

Modeling Microreactors Using OpenSn: An Open Source Discrete-Ordinates Code (S_N)

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ABSTRACT

With the growing interest in microreactors, there is an increasing need for accurate and efficient multi-physics modeling to capture the coupled effects of neutronics, thermomechanics, and fluid dynamics within these advanced systems. The Monte Carlo radiation transport code Serpent2 supports coupling with OpenFOAM, a framework for computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and thermal-mechanical analysis. However, while Monte Carlo simulations offer high-fidelity solutions, they are often computationally expensive, since achieving adequate statistical convergence in every mesh cell is necessary to ensure accurate feedback in coupled multiphysics problems. To address this limitation, OpenSn, an open-source discrete ordinates (S_N) code developed at Texas A&M University, has been extended to read and operate on OpenFOAM meshes, marking a key step toward enabling fully coupled multiphysics simulations. In this study, OpenSn was employed to compute the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}) and its scalar flux of an eVinci-style microreactor, with the results compared against those obtained using an equivalent Serpent2 model. Furthermore, the effective compute time in which these results were obtained were compared. The S_N solver in OpenSn demonstrates strong potential for iterative reactor design analyses by providing accurate solutions with reduced computational cost relative to pure Monte Carlo approaches.

Keywords: microreactors, OpenSn, Serpent2, criticality

1. INTRODUCTION

The interest in small modular reactors (SMRs) and microreactors has grown as a viable alternative energy source that comes with a low carbon footprint and a lower initial capital exposure with respect to traditional light water reactors. Additionally, micro-reactors are well suited for powering remote areas while an emerging application for SMRs, driven by the rise of artificial intelligence, is the growing demand for localized power to support large-scale data centers. Following these trends, recent years have seen significant private and public investment with aims at commercializing these advanced reactor technologies [1, 2]. Companies such as X-energy, BWXT Advanced Technologies, and Westinghouse Electric Company all have their respective microreactor designs: X-energy's XENITH, BWXT's BANR, and Westinghouse's eVinci reactor [3][4][5].

However, with the deployment of these new nuclear systems comes rigorous analysis and development to meet safety regulations and guidelines imposed by federal regulators. This typically consists of running thermal fluids, radiation transport, and systems codes at various levels of fidelity to predict the operational capability and safety of a reactor design [6]. Furthermore, in modeling the neutronics of microreactors and some SMR concepts, the diffusion approximation can be inadequate due to the collapse in its underlying assumptions. A compact core size leads to increased neutron leakage and stronger spatial heterogeneity, resulting in steep flux gradients and pronounced angular anisotropies. Under these conditions the diffusion model can lead to systematic errors in the prediction of the neutron scalar flux distribution, reactivity coefficients, and spectral effects [7]. Consequently, higher-fidelity transport

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methods, such as Monte Carlo simulations or discrete-ordinates (S_N), can be preferable to accurately capture neutron behavior in microreactors. While Monte Carlo solutions are generally more accurate than S_N , the associated computational resources required can be expensive for design iterations. This constraint is exacerbated by the need for sufficient statistical convergence in each element of potentially large meshes in multiphysics contexts.

To address these modeling challenges, the focus in this paper is primarily that of radiation transport modeling using OpenSn, an open-source discrete ordinates (S_N) solver developed at Texas A&M University [8]. The objective is to demonstrate and test the performances and accuracy of the OpenSn discrete-ordinates solver in computing the k_{eff} and scalar flux on a realistic microreactor model in comparison to Serpent2 [9]. In addition, we present an extension of OpenSn to read OpenFOAM-based meshes, a first step towards fully-deterministic high-fidelity multiphysics simulations based on open-source software. OpenFOAM has been selected thanks to its open-source license, state-of-the-art CFD and structural mechanics capabilities, and extensive user community [10]. The choice of using Serpent2 as the Monte Carlo code is motivated by its existing ability to interface with OpenFOAM.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Geometry and Materials

The geometry is derived from an eVinci-type heat-pipe microreactor concept, with the reflector and control drums excluded [11]. These components were omitted for two reasons: first, to simplify the problem for this initial study; and second, because the increased scattering associated with the reflector would significantly increase the computational cost in Serpent2, while having comparatively negligible impact on the OpenSn solution time. It consists of hexagonal assemblies. Each assembly consists of 24 fuel-compact rods and 7 heat pipes compacted into hexagonal matrix of graphite, with the total number of assemblies being 127. The pin pitch is 2.782 (cm), the assembly pitch is 17.368 (cm), and the total height of the core is 1.6 (m). The fuel compact radii are 0.95 (cm) and the heat pipes have a radii of 1.07 (cm). The mesh was generated using the open-source SALOME platform and represented one-fourth of the core to exploit the rotational symmetry of the system. The meshed geometry is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The fuel compact, heat pipes, graphite and void regions are colored as blue (3), yellow (0), red (1), and green (2) respectively. 916,160 total cells.

The heat pipes were modeled as SS316 that were void-filled rather than sodium-filled, due to the lack of available data regarding the precise amount of working fluid expected in the system, and the low cross-sections of sodium. The fuel compact was composed of TRISO fuel particles embedded within a

graphite matrix. For modeling purposes, it was treated as a homogeneous mixture of UCO, PyC, SiC, and graphite, corresponding to a packing fraction of 0.4. Helium is included in the fuel composition to account for the buffer. Likewise, the heat pipes were also homogenized. All the material compositions used in the model are shown in Table I. A more accurate homogenization of the TRISO fuel compact can be obtained using the reactivity-equivalent physical transformation (RPT) method, which explicitly treats the double heterogeneity inherent to the fuel [12].

Table I. Material densities and compositions.

Material	Density (g/cc)	Volume Fraction
Fuel Compact (vol. avg.)	2.020	1.000
UCO	10.744	0.042
Graphite	1.040	0.649
PyC	1.882	0.243
SiC	3.168	0.006
He	3.25×10^{-4}	0.102
Graphite	1.806	1.000
Heat Pipe (vol. avg.)	1.084	1.000
SS316	7.670	0.141
He	3.25×10^{-4}	0.859

2.2. Serpent Modeling

In this study, Serpent2, a Monte Carlo transport software, was employed to perform two distinct simulations. The first consisted of an infinite lattice calculation used to generate multigroup macroscopic cross-sections for each material to be provided as input to OpenSn. The second involved simulating the transport of neutrons on an unstructured mesh representing the finite reactor core. The objective of the second Monte Carlo simulation was to establish a reference case for comparison with OpenSn results and required computational resources. For both Serpent2 simulations, a total of 2×10^9 particle histories were simulated to achieve a statistical uncertainty of 10 pcm in the resulting k_{eff} . The ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library was used, and the cross-sections utilized were at 300 K [13].

In the infinite lattice calculation, the model was constructed using Constructive Solid Geometry, which is the built-in method to define geometries through Boolean operations. The multigroup cross-sections were generated using the SCALE 44 energy group structure [14].

For the eigenvalue calculation on the finite core, the multiphysics interface provided by Serpent2 was exploited. This interface allows for the simulation of neutron transport on unstructured OpenFOAM meshes. The material properties can be defined and reaction rates can be tallied at a cell-by-cell level within the mesh. Periodic boundary conditions were applied at the symmetry planes, while vacuum boundary conditions were imposed at the surface of a cylinder enclosing the domain of the problem. The energy integrated neutron flux was tallied and then scaled to the operating power of the eVinci-like microreactor, which is 15 MWth.

An additional third simulation was conducted to tally the neutron flux into energy bins according to the SCALE 44 energy group structure. This simulation was not run to completion, but it was used to assess the computational time required by Serpent2 to compute multigroup fluxes. All of the Serpent2 calculations were performed on the Idaho National Laboratory (INL), high-performance computing (HPC) machine, *Bitterroot*.

2.3. OpenSn Modeling

The OpenFOAM mesh reader implementation introduced in this paper was used in OpenSn to import the same mesh employed in the Serpent2 model. The multigroup cross sections generated from the infinite-lattice calculation were assigned to the fuel compact, heat pipes, and graphite regions via the block IDs defined in the mesh. This was achieved through the reading of the `cellZones` file within the `polyMesh` directory during the mesh conversion process in OpenSn, executed by the `FromFileMeshGenerator`. For the void region, the cross-sections for the graphite were modified by a factor of $1e-8$ to mimic the low density helium.

A total of six calculations were performed with OpenSn. OpenSn currently offers Gauss-Legendre-Chebyshev and Lebedev quadrature sets, with plans to implement Galerkin quadrature sets. For this work, standard three-dimensional Gauss-Legendre-Chebyshev quadrature sets were employed for the S_4 , S_8 , and S_{16} calculations. These correspond to 4 polar and 8 azimuthal angles for S_4 , 8 polar and 16 azimuthal angles for S_8 , and 16 polar and 32 azimuthal angles for S_{16} . Furthermore, P_0 and P_1 scattering models were applied for both the S_4 and S_8 calculations. An additional S_{16}, P_1 calculation was performed to examine the convergence of the angular discretization, while an S_8, P_3 calculation was carried out to assess the effects of anisotropic scattering.

The `NonLinearKEigenSolver` in OpenSn was utilized to solve the eigenvalue problem. The solver utilizes a piecewise linear Discontinuous-Galerkin (DG) finite element approximation for the spatial discretization. The solver was set with a maximum of 50 outer iterations and 20 inner iterations, and an absolute tolerance of 10^{-8} . The solver employed a Generalized Minimal Residual (GMRES) preconditioner to accelerate convergence, with a maximum of 300 iterations, an absolute tolerance of 10^{-6} , and a restart interval of 30. All OpenSn simulations were conducted on the Texas A&M High Performance Research Computing (HPRC) system, *Faster*.

2.4. Differences in HPC Resources

The fact that the simulations were executed on different machines must be taken into account when comparing compute times. For a fair performance comparison, both codes should ideally be run on the same hardware platform; however, this was not feasible due to export control and licensing restrictions. It should also be noted that the two methods exhibit different computational bottlenecks: Monte Carlo calculations are generally more sensitive to processor performance, while S_N calculations are typically limited by memory throughput. Table II summarizes the hardware specifications for each machine.

Table II. HPC Specifications

Machine	Nodes	Cores per Node	Memory (GB)	CPUs
Bitterroot (INL)	384	112	256	Sapphire Rapids 56-core
Faster (TAMU)	180	64	256	Ice Lake 32-core

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The Serpent2 one group model was used as a baseline for comparison with OpenSn calculations. The P_0 models for the S_4 and S_8 calculations differs from the Serpent2 calculation by 2,675 (pcm), while the calculations with a P_1 model are all within about 560 (pcm) of the Serpent2 calculation. The differences between the P_1 models for S_4 , S_8 , and S_{16} were negligible, within roughly 10 (pcm) of one another. These results indicated that applying a P_1 scattering model is necessary in computing an accurate k_{eff} . This was expected due to the forward-peaked nature of the scattering in graphite, which the P_1 spherical

harmonics capture. Additionally, it can be observed that the S_4 angular discretization is sufficient to gain k_{eff} to model error. The observed discrepancy in k_{eff} can be attributed to model error from the inaccuracies in the multi-group cross sections, as each assembly was treated with the same neutron spectra. A more effective approach would involve generating distinct material cross sections based on concentric rings of assemblies and axial groups, as this method more accurately captures the spatial variations in the neutron spectra experienced by each assembly. The result from the S_8, P_3 calculation actually deviates more from the Serpent2 reference than the P_1 models. However, the difference is minimal, indicating that increasing the scattering order beyond P_1 is not necessary.

Table III. Resulting k_{eff} and compute times.

Model	k_{eff} (pcm)	Nodes	Cores/Node	Wall Time (h)	Δk_{eff} (w.r.t. Serpent2 in pcm)
Serpent2 (1G)	1.02126 ± 9	15	20	8.667	-
Serpent2 (44G)	-	15	20	100	-
$S_4 P_0$	1.048000	8	48	0.433	-2674
$S_4 P_1$	1.026817	8	48	0.583	- 556
$S_8 P_0$	1.048012	8	48	1.467	-2675
$S_8 P_1$	1.026880	8	48	1.717	-562
$S_{16} P_1$	1.026874	8	48	6.478	-561
$S_8 P_3$	1.026988	8	48	3.067	-573

The total scalar fluxes were also compared between the Serpent2 calculation and the OpenSn $S_4 P_1$, $S_8 P_1$, $S_{16} P_1$, and $S_8 P_3$ calculations. Although angular discretization has a relatively minor influence on k_{eff} , an integral quantity, it can significantly influence the spatial distribution of the scalar flux. In particular, S_N calculations can exhibit a phenomenon known as ray effects which arise from angular discretization error. Ray effects are most pronounced in problems featuring highly localized sources, strongly anisotropic scattering, and neutronicly thin media. While fission sources are largely isotropic (making this effect less significant), graphite exhibits forward-peaked scattering. Moreover, because the system is compact, neutrons experience relatively few scattering interactions and leak from the boundaries before thermalization. This results in directionally biased flux distributions at higher energies. The total scalar flux profiles in the center XY-plane and XZ-plane for the Serpent2, $S_4 P_1$, $S_8 P_1$, $S_{16} P_1$, and $S_8 P_3$ are shown in Figures 2 and 3.

The Serpent2 results displayed in Figures 2a and 3a have an average statistical uncertainty of 0.47%, with a maximum uncertainty of 5%. The OpenSn results shown in Figures 2b, 2c and 2d demonstrate that increasing the angular discretization reduces the magnitude of the observed ray effects in the radial direction, specifically at the north-east corner of the core. This effect is also observed in the axial direction, as shown in Figures 3b, 3c and 3d. The apparent noise in the axial scalar flux profile is likely a consequence of the low axial resolution, since the domain was discretized with only sixteen axial cells. The differences between the $S_8 P_1$ and $S_8 P_3$ calculations is negligible, with very little observed difference in the total scalar flux distribution as seen in Figures 2c and 2e, and 3c and 3e. Additionally, there is good agreement between the Serpent2 and OpenSn total scalar flux distributions within the reactor core, showing that an $S_4 P_1$ calculation is likely sufficient. However, if the quantity of interest lies outside the reactor core, such as in shielding calculations, an $S_8 P_1$ or $S_{16} P_1$ calculation might be preferred, as there is a minimization in the observable ray effects in regions beyond the core as shown in Figures 2c and 2d. There are also ongoing developments to introduce acceleration techniques tailored to k-eigenvalue problems, which are expected to further reduce compute times. It should be mentioned that some of the observed discrepancies between the OpenSn and Serpent2 results may stem in part from ParaView

post-processing artifacts: an initial Serpent2 visualization showed zero-valued regions near the domain extremities that are not present in the underlying Serpent2 output data.

Figure 2. Scalar flux profiles in the center XY-plane (log-scaled).

Figure 3. Scalar flux profiles in the XZ-plane (log-scaled).

OpenSn calculations converged within minutes to a few hours, whereas the Serpent2 1-group case took 9 hours. Furthermore, the Serpent2 44-group case was estimated to require nearly 100 hours of wall time for the same number of particle histories as the 1-group Serpent2 model, while OpenSn directly provides the multigroup fluxes. Because the statistical uncertainty in Monte Carlo calculations decreases only with the inverse square root of the number of particle histories, achieving comparable precision would demand an impractically large number of histories. These results collectively demonstrate that OpenSn achieves comparable accuracy to Serpent2 at a fraction of the computational cost, making it well suited for high-fidelity, iterative design workflows.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrated the capability of the open-source discrete ordinates code OpenSn to perform high-fidelity neutron transport calculations on OpenFOAM-based meshes, representing a key step toward fully deterministic, open-source multiphysics modeling. The new mesh interface enables consistent geometry between OpenSn and OpenFOAM, establishing a unified framework for future neutronic-thermal-mechanical coupling.

OpenSn produced results that are promising and broadly consistent with Serpent2 reference calculations for an eVinci-style microreactor, showing reasonable agreement in both k_{eff} and scalar flux while completing calculations in a fraction of the runtime. The $S_4 P_1$ model was found sufficient for criticality calculations. However, the agreement is not yet considered final, and additional studies of mesh convergence and spatial variation in multigroup cross sections are needed to better understand remaining discrepancies. By directly producing multigroup fluxes without statistical tallies, OpenSn offers a computationally efficient and transparent approach for reactor analysis. Future work will focus on mesh convergence studies, the incorporation of spatially and temperature-dependent multigroup cross sections, the generation of cell-averaged power density maps in an OpenFOAM-compatible input format, and validation against benchmark experiments to further extend OpenSn's multiphysics capabilities.

NOMENCLATURE

S_N	Discrete-ordinates
<i>CFD</i>	Computational fluid dynamics
<i>HPC</i>	High performance computing
k_{eff}	Multiplication factor
<i>pcm</i>	Percent mille

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